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Transformative governance cultures? Explaining variation in regional climate change responses with culture

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Abstract

The need for transformative adaptation is beyond question, but its regional implementation remains a pressing issue. While heterogenous climate impacts obviously demand tailored approaches, we argue that varying governance cultures are an equally important, yet understudied variable to explain and develop region-specific climate change responses. Using the concept of policy arrangements, we investigate the three European mountain regions Lapland, Tyrol, and Râu Sadului/Sibiu to analyse how region-specific governance idiosyncrasies influence adaptation. We find that entrenched routines, established coalitions and dominant framings play into regional climate governance just as much as region-specific climate change impacts, material dependencies, and economic pressures. We hence call for greater awareness of these aspects in researching and designing governance approaches for transformative change.

Keywords

transformative
governance;
regional climate
change adaptation;
spatial
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mountain regions;
policy
arrangements

Introduction

Climate change adaptation (CCA) is key for the future viability of regions. However, while constituting a multi-level governance issue (Hanssen et al., 2013; Nalau et al., 2015), the regional level has long been overlooked as a central scale for adaptation processes (Juhola et al., 2012). Yet, regionalised responses to adaptation are essential for transformative change, as they allow to connect and scale local adaptation capacities, while building on shared knowledge to

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challenge entrenched policies and practices (Dannevig & Aall, 2015; Granberg et al., 2019a; Bonnett & Birchall, 2023). Analytically, a regionalized perspective also opens up opportunities to differentiate between climate change responses depending on place-bound conditions and challenges.

That being said, studies on regional CCA are still often falling short in adequately considering place-bound factors and their impact on policy formulation and adaptation governance. This particularly pertains to the socio-cultural dimension, that is, collectively shared symbols and values that drive societal beliefs, rituals and storytelling – all potentially influencing whether and how CCA is being addressed, by what means and to what end (Adger et al., 2013). While the role of the socio-cultural dimension in regional CCA has already been discussed, these studies predominantly emphasise either behavioural change on an individual and household level based on cultural aspects, or apply comprehensive anthropological perspectives on the concept of culture(s) and regional identity in relation to climate change and issues of transformation (Ensor & Berger, 2009; Fresque-Baxter & Armitage, 2012; Marshall et al., 2012; Barnett et al., 2021). Hence, while it is agreed upon that culture plays a significant part in regional climate change responses, the influence of specific regional *governance* cultures in this regard has not yet been addressed to a satisfying degree.

Neglecting the influence of regionally entrenched, self-evident ways of approaching transformation issues might lead to maladaptive outcomes or ineffectiveness of adaptation actions (Marshall et al., 2012; Adger et al., 2013; McNeeley & Lazrus, 2014; Gorddard et al., 2016). We argue that by taking a cultural perspective on regional climate governance, regional dependencies and differences in climate change adaptation can be better addressed and more tailored approaches to transformative regional governance can be developed.

Building on insights from the EU-funded project MountResilience (MountResilience, n.d.), we approach our objective through studying the three European regions Lapland (Finland), Tyrol (Austria) and Râu Sadului/Sibiu (Romania). Thereby, we take a focus on mountain regions, as they are especially vulnerable to climate change and in need of fast, efficient and effective CCA actions to foster the adaptive capacities of local communities (Ingold et al., 2010). Despite different climate scenarios, all three regions are likely to experience serious consequences in sectors that are fundamental to both their prosperity and identity. Transformative change is therefore a pressing issue and a key reason why all three are making considerable efforts in CCA. Our comparative analysis is rooted in the concept of policy arrangements (Arts, Leroy, & van Tatenhove, 2006). This approach allows to assess the actors, resources, discourses and “rules of the game” of regional adaptation governance. In doing so, we can determine which factors –

both “hard” and “soft” – inform a regional transformative governance culture and how they challenge spatial transformations.

We begin with an overview of the literature on regional governance, CCA governance and the recent call for transformative approaches, and further point out the role of place-bound socio-cultural factors for regional transformations. Then, we introduce the concept of policy arrangements as our analytical lens, and the material and methods used for the analysis. Presenting and discussing our results in the following section, we point out major aspects of transformative governance cultures with regards to the substance and organisation of policy domains and regional discourses. Finally, we draw conclusions and point out important implications for future research on transformative governance cultures and spatial transformations.

Literature review: From regional adaptation to cultures of transformative governance

Regional governance for tailored policymaking and implementation

While general literature on *regional* governance differs in its focus and approach, it has common ground in encompassing a system of institutions, organisations, and normative constructs that shape specific policy areas (Nolte, 2016). Regional governance also symbolizes an awareness of regional difference in development patterns that calls for regional differentiation in policymaking (Morrison, 2014). As an analytical concept, it examines how and by what means regional institutions interact and engage with internal and external actors to develop and implement policy objectives in concrete fields of political action (Christopoulos, 2006). Assessments of regional governance hence also enable in-depth elaborations of change processes and patterns of change in different regional contexts (cf. Morrison, 2014).

While regional governance typically focuses on horizontal coordination for effective policymaking, *multi-level* governance emphasises the significance of vertical coherence across levels to cater for regional development. In general, it is defined by both the structure of a system and the interaction among its different levels (Benz and Eberlein, 1999). Research on multi-level governance hence has a marked interest in regional dynamics of federalism and the state (Hooghe and Marks, 2003). It also focuses on the relation of regional development and supranational actors such as the European Union (Shakel, 2020). The challenge of multi-level governance for effective CCA has also been widely debated in the past two decades (cf. for instance Gupta, 2007; Termeer et al., 2016).

In recent years, however, authors have been observing the rise of a new kind of regionalism that is marked by a stronger political and institutional structure rather than by economic

arrangements (Lachapelle and Oñate, 2018). They point towards the relevance of cultural factors, such as regional identities, that lead to a reinforcement of local and regional focal points for development and collective action. This implies that effective governance is not just a question of horizontal and vertical coordination in technical terms of policymaking, but also a question of embedding and negotiation vis-à-vis regional idiosyncrasies, identities and values.

Climate change adaptation and the need for transformative governance

While CCA has played a subordinate role in the first decade of climate policies, it has risen up on the global public agenda since the early 2000s (Schipper, 2006; Khan & Roberts, 2013; Lesniowski et al., 2017). After issuing a series of non-legislative forms of policy around adaptation, the EU has published its first Adaptation Strategy in 2013 (Directorate-General for Climate Action, n.d.). In response to the EU's impetus, EU Member states have started developing National Adaptation Strategies, stating political commitment to adaptation at the national policy level (Biesbroek et al., 2010). However, as climate change impacts are particularly experienced at the local level, adaptation governance and implementation have long been framed as a primarily local concern (Aguar et al., 2018; Granberg et al., 2019a), often leading to isolated, narrowly focused and short-term-oriented adaptation actions (Nalau et al., 2015; McDowell et al., 2019). Given that climate impacts are not confined to administrative boundaries (Benzie & Persson, 2019) and that effective climate change responses require a multi-level governance approach (Amundsen et al., 2010; Nalau et al., 2015; Persson, 2019), local aspects of adaptation governance have increasingly been challenged. Instead, scholars call for regional adaptation governance (Bauer & Steurer, 2014; Shi, 2019). Moreover, in the face of growing climate-related threats, established adaptation efforts are increasingly considered insufficient (IPCC, 2023). The prevailing economic and political structures and cognitive limits to envisioning alternative pathways pose significant barriers to change at desired speed and depth (Chaffin et al., 2016). Dissatisfied with the dominance of business-as-usual approaches, scholars and practitioners thus increasingly call for a transformative approach to adaptation that aims for fundamental shifts in systems, processes, norms, and cultures (Pelling et al., 2015; Fedele et al., 2019; Filho et al., 2023). This includes changes in governance approaches (Kelemen et al., 2023).

In this context, transformative governance has become a collective term for approaches that promote accelerated, system-sensitive and deep-seated change (cf. Chaffin et al., 2016; Patterson et al., 2017). Though lacking a precise definition, debates on transformative governance uniformly call for broader perspectives towards processual dynamics, experimentation and learning, collaborative modes of knowledge production and co-creation, as

well as local agency and systems-thinking, as regional adaptation processes need to go beyond coping and business-as-usual-oriented responses to allow for fundamental change (Fedele et al., 2019; Horcea-Milku et al., 2024).

Transformative governance is thus understood as an approach that does not seek to ensure stability but has the capacity to steer a fundamental change in social-ecological systems by addressing the root causes of unsustainability (Visseren-Hamakers et al., 2021). This requires an approach that bridges issues, scales, sectors and places, challenges entrenched institutional frameworks, is inclusive of pluralistic values, builds on multiple actors' capacities, and embraces reflexivity and learning (Kelemen et al., 2023; Pascual et al., 2022). Stronger collaboration and a clear "social contract" defining roles and responsibilities have thus been called for to enhance multi-actor governance and equitable adaptation – especially in regions with high climate vulnerability (Petzold et al., 2023). Importantly, scholars are increasingly pointing to the integral role of values in transformative governance (Kelemen et al., 2023). They stress that governing transformative change requires major changes in entrenched values and beliefs (Kelemen et al., 2023; Visseren-Hamakers et al., 2021). A cultural lens on transformative governance that takes the traditional, routinised and deeply entrenched modes to governing regional change seriously is thus relevant to make sense of the variability of approaches and their respective spatial implications. The need for a more differentiated adaptation governance perspective is thus without question (Granberg et al., 2019a).

A cultural lens on transformative regional governance

Transformative regional governance is attributed a mediating and coordinating role, driving CCA at the local scale (Hanssen et al., 2013; Granberg et al., 2019b; Vogel et al., 2020; Bonnett & Birchall, 2023) while supporting transformative change on higher scales (Granberg et al., 2019b). Actions at the local scale are deeply tied to questions of culture and representation (Duncan and Ley, 1993). Therefore, a change of the normative structures that guide governance responses is also deeply embedded in regional values, the reflexivity, normative and inner dimensions of actors (Horcea-Milku et al., 2024). Being more than a technical issue, transformative governance therefore needs to address socio-culturally embedded processes, including multiple formal and informal actors, learning processes, values and interests (Eriksen et al., 2015) to effectively guide regional change. Adger et al. (2013) have already stressed that risk awareness, adaptation responses, and means of implementation are all mediated by culture, thus arguing that the understanding of culture is essential to reflect on the differing human responses to climate change. Scholars have also pointed out that identities play a critical role in shaping adaptation processes, acting as both enablers and constraints of adaptation

actions (Marshall et al., 2012; Barnett et al., 2021) and in perceiving environmental and social challenges (McNeeley & Lazrus, 2014; Quinn et al., 2019). More recently, Marks et al. (2022) have stressed the importance of cultural, context-sensitive factors to better address vulnerability. However, for the most part, studies using cultural explanations of regional CCA either refer to value-rationalities on the individual or household level, or anthropological conceptions of culture(s) as overarching conceptions of regional specificity in dealing with climate change (Ensor & Berger, 2009; Fresque-Baxter & Armitage, 2012; Marshall et al., 2012; Barnett et al., 2021). Hence, while CCA literature is increasingly incorporating socio-cultural and socio-political factors into explanations of the success and failure of regional climate change responses, a cultural perspective explaining regional variation in transformative *governance* is still largely lacking. We argue that such entrenched idiosyncrasies in the values, framings, and routines of regional governance influence the ways in which transformative change is being governed. We hence refer to this regional variation as transformative governance cultures.

For analysing transformative governance arrangements in their material and cultural dimensions, we employ the policy arrangements framework (Arts, Leroy, & Van Tatenhove, 2006; Arts & Van Tatenhove, 2000). It enables cultural explanations of why CCA approaches differ from region to region, while not neglecting the material dependencies of agency in transformative endeavours (Van Assche et al., 2022). In the following section, we will expand on the concept of policy arrangements as our analytical lens and introduce the three case studies.

Methodology and case rationale

Analytical framework: Policy arrangements

While there are multiple approaches to study regional governance dynamics, these often tend to exclude the socio-cultural dimension and place-bound preferences of governing stability and change. We employ the policy arrangements approach (Arts, Leroy, & van Tatenhove, 2006; Arts & Van Tatenhove, 2000) as an analytical framework to study regional CCA governance. The policy arrangements approach is sensitive towards broader organisational configurations as well as the underlying norms and implicit and explicit rules of regional governance, hence constituting a suitable lens to assess regional variation in climate change governance responses. The concept has traditionally been used to address dynamics of stability and change in (regional) environmental policies (ibid.). It has since been applied to various sub-fields of climate and environmental governance, including nature policy (Zouwen, 2006), water management (Wiering & Immink, 2006), forest management (Veenman et al., 2009), agriculture (Contesse et al., 2018), and green infrastructure management (Buijs et al., 2019), but also regional planning (van Straalen

et al., 2016), making it a fitting approach to study transformative governance cultures in the context of regional CCA.

The policy arrangements approach distinguishes between four dimensions of analysis: actors, resources, discourse, and “rules of the game” (Table 1). The *actors* dimension denominates relevant stakeholders who are directly or indirectly involved in or excluded from the policy domain, as well as their formation in coalitions sharing similar goals (Arts & Van Tatenhove, 2000; Veenman et al., 2009). *Resources* refers to the division and distribution of (access to) knowledge, money or skills for policy development (Veenman et al., 2009). It is therefore inherently linked to questions of power and influence in regional governance (Arts, Leroy, & van Tatenhove, 2006). *Discourse* is the interpretive lens for dominant policy concepts and story lines “by which meaning is given to a policy domain” (Arts & Van Tatenhove, 2004, p. 343). Through an assessment of regional discourse, the wider socio-political realities and different policy responses can hence be reflected and addressed (van Hulst et al., 2024). *Rules of the game* includes both formal and informal rules and regulations of policy- and decision-making that define the leeway of involved actors within a field (Arts, Leroy, & van Tatenhove, 2006). These four dimensions are understood as closely interrelated. For instance, rules and resources determine the capacity of actors to address and frame emerging problems “as political and policy problems, and to mobilise resources” while also contributing to their solution (Arts & Van Tatenhove, 2004, p. 351). Such framings are of key significance for transformative regional governance, as our cases are about to show.

Table 1 – Understanding of policy arrangements in transformative regional climate governance (own illustration)

Dimensions	Guiding questions of case study analysis
Actors	Who are the key actors involved in CCA governance? What roles and responsibilities are they assigned with?
Resources	What material and non-material resources, e.g., knowledge, experience, finances, competencies, are being leveraged for regional CCA governance?
Discourse	How is regional CCA being framed and problematised? What are dominant conceptions of the region, its identity, and its future, and how do they inform CCA governance?
Rules of the game	What are the implicit, routinised approaches to “good regional governance” and how do they influence the formation of resources, actors, and discourses in transformative climate governance?

Empirical material: Climate governance in three mountain regions

Mountain regions are especially vulnerable to climate change and severely affected by rapid changes in their social-ecological systems (Vij et al., 2021). While they share a common challenge, adaptation governance approaches still need to be tailored to concrete climate impacts and, as explained above, embedded in place-bound governance cultures.

Building on insights from the EU-funded project MountResilience (MountResilience, n.d.), we study CCA governance in the three European mountain regions Tyrol (Austria), Lapland (Finland), and Râu Sadului in Sibiu (Romania). The following considerations informed the case selection: (1) All three are significantly affected by climate change in the key sectors of tourism and agriculture, which are both substantial foundations to these regions' economies and prosperity, and integral to their identity. (2) They all have prominently formulated the goal of tackling the challenges presented by climate change in a transformative way. (3) Knowledgeable regional stakeholders were willing to share information, and relevant data for assessing regional CCA according to the policy arrangements framework was accessible to a satisfying degree. Case selection was thus a middle ground between the aim of comparing several regions that share similar development challenges associated with climate change, and the pragmatic issue of data availability and accessibility.

The analyses were conducted between September 2023 and September 2024. The policy arrangements were studied through (1) extensive desk research on the respective multilevel governance configurations, regional structural and social-ecological system conditions, regional climate change projections, and risk and vulnerability assessments.¹ This step was complemented with (2) screenings of regional policy documents such as development concepts, strategies, or plans associated with climate change and climate change adaptation (n=41). The selection was guided by tacit knowledge of regional project partners. Documents were identified both through our own initial desk research and an online scoping survey with regional project partners using SurveyMonkey software. This was complemented with additional bilateral discussions with selected partners to assess the relevance of specific documents. Consequently, strategies with high relevance for regional CCA (n=10) were analysed in-depth. Regional and national documents were included insofar as they provided guidance to regional adaptation, even if they were not explicitly framed as adaptation strategies. As municipal documents were mostly not explicitly referring to adaptation, they were only partially included in the analysis if agreed upon with the respective knowledgeable regional partners. Through

¹ At the time being, there were no comprehensive risk and vulnerability assessments available on regional level for either of the three cases. Hence, this information had to be incorporated through secondary data sources.

qualitative content analysis using MAXQDA, data on regional climate change governance, central visions and priorities for adaptation in the respective regions were coded deductively (see Annex for coding scheme).

Building on that, (3) expert interviews with regional stakeholders were conducted (cf. Bogner et al., 2009) to derive information on the implicit dimensions of the respective policy arrangements and sentiments towards regional CCA governance (n=23; see Annex for interview guideline). In consultation with our regional project partners, a longlist of potentially relevant stakeholders – developed through prior desk research and content analysis – was boiled down to shortlists of 5-10 knowledgeable actors per region. Interviewees were selected according to their local, experiential or expert knowledge on region-specific climate impacts, CCA and governance issues and hence ranged from local authorities and non-governmental organisations to regional experts on CCA, regional development (e.g. tourism), infrastructure and nature conservation. Interviews were conducted online via Zoom or Teams in English or the interviewees' respective mother tongue with assistance in translating from regional project partners. The conversations were recorded, transcribed and coded deductively using the same code scheme as for the analysis of policy documents (see Annex), although additional relevant statements beyond the existing codes were also sporadically incorporated into the code database, e.g., if they spoke to certain sentiments towards CCA or regional governance in general. (4) Three regional online validation workshops (one per case study region) further enabled reflecting our assessments of the policy arrangements and deepen our understanding of regional governance cultures and their influence on spatial transformations in the respective regions (cf. Kalbach et al., 2018). The online format allowed the participation of a broad audience, notwithstanding their (often remote) location, to verify, complement and discuss our findings.

This multistage research design allowed for an in-depth, context-sensitive exploration of regional governance processes. The use of a coding scheme ensured analytical consistency and helped identify patterns in institutional language, norms, and strategic orientations in the screened documents, while the interviews and workshops allowed for gaining and verifying inside perspectives on governance practices, decision-making rationales, and perceived challenges, offering insights that are typically absent from formal documentation.

The following chapter presents the results for each region.

Results²

Tyrol

Tyrol is one of nine Austrian federal provinces. It is located in the eastern part of the European Alps, hence characterized by a mountainous landscape with high peaks, glaciers and deep valleys with limited permanent settlement areas. Climate projections foresee warming at a higher rate than the global average (Brunetti et al., 2009) and, relatedly, decreasing soil stability and fertility, endangerment of alpine habitats and biodiversity, and changes in the hydrosphere (Landeshauptstadt Innsbruck, 2020). While Tyrol lacks a comprehensive risk and vulnerability assessment, it is clear that rising temperatures are driving the retreat of glaciers and increasing the risk of natural hazards in the region. Reduced snow-reliability and snow-cover pose a particular challenge for Tyrol's economically important winter tourism. Alongside the industrial sector, tourism is a key source of income and employment in the region, particularly in the more remote areas of the province (Abegg et al., 2007; Steiger & Trawöger, 2011; Hohenwallner et al., 2015). In contrast, the densely populated Inn Valley, with Tyrol's capital city Innsbruck, has become especially vulnerable to increasing temperatures (Chimani et al., 2016). Here, heat days are projected to double by 2071, which will severely increase heat stress for the urban population (Landeshauptstadt Innsbruck, 2020).

As Austria is a federal state, formal competencies are shared between the state and its provinces (and, due to the principle of subsidiarity, partly also municipalities). Climate change mitigation and adaptation are not explicitly addressed in the Austrian constitution. Hence the distribution of competencies depends on the field of action. Consequently, Tyrol can enact and enforce laws within its sole areas of responsibility, which include a range of domains, such as building law and housing subsidies, spatial planning, nature and landscape protection and tourism (Alberton et al., 2022).

While Tyrol thus holds formal competencies for a range of adaptation-relevant domains, the municipalities constitute the key *actors*. They are primarily held responsible for CCA, which points to Tyrol's localised approach to adaptation (TI1b; TI4; TI8). Based on a national funding program for CCA in model regions (*KLAR!*), *KLAR!*-managers have been installed in twelve sub-regions in Tyrol, which are composed of 3 to 33 municipalities each. *KLAR!*-managers are tasked with the development of regional adaptation concepts and the implementation of pre-defined projects (Klima- und Energiefonds, 2024), many of which focus on the building of knowledge and raising awareness for CCA issues (TI4; TI7). As intermediary actors, the *KLAR!*-managers don't

²For readability, references to empirical material in this section are abbreviated with the first letter of the region, plus "D" for document, "I" for interview, or "VDWS" for validation workshop, and consecutive numbers for specific documents and interviews. A complete list of documents and interviews can be found in the Annex.

hold formal competencies for adaptation and remain dependent on the political authorities' voluntary commitment to CCA. Besides that, actors from the public sector and various interest groups from different economic sectors such as tourism, marketing or agriculture appear as key advocates of specific interests and objectives towards regional adaptation in Tyrol (TI4; TI5; TI6).

In terms of governance *resources*, due to the federal system, multi-level governance networks are traditionally well established. At the same time, these configurations give rise to certain expectations as to how new issues (such as CCA) should be tackled. In economic terms, Tyrol is generally well-equipped with financial resources that can be leveraged for CCA (Eurostat, 2022). However, municipal budgets are constrained, hence pre-financing adaptation measures constitutes a major challenge (TI8). Additionally, the region draws on relevant expertise and experiential knowledge from decades of profound engagement with natural hazard management (TI1a). Furthermore, Tyrol has adopted its first strategy on climate protection and adaptation a decade ago, reflecting the region's experience in tackling the issues on the level of regional governance.

As concerns *discourse*, the Sustainability and Climate Strategy (TD1) and its accompanying Action Plan (TD2) represent the two major strategic documents specifically addressing CCA, although they only treat adaptation superficially, as was also critically mentioned in a number of interviews (TI1b; TI3). CCA discourse in Tyrol can be characterized as predominantly economically driven. Tyrol's alpine landscape is central to the region's identity and self-image, as well as to tourism and, consequently, the regional economy (TI2; TI4; TI7). The changing climate is thus perceived as a potential threat to both regional identity and key regional economic sectors. Yet, the framing of adaptation is conspicuously positive, aiming to turn the necessity to adapt into a virtue by "reducing vulnerability to climate change and increasing resilience as well as making use of the positive effects of a changing climate" (TD1, p. 51, translation by the authors). Proactive adaptation is considered an "engine for regional economic cycles and sustainable products and technologies" (ibid., p. 55, translation by the authors), posing an opportunity for Tyrol to become a pioneer in CCA by developing "into the most sustainable and climate-friendly tourism region in the Alps" (ibid., p. 47, translation by the authors). The Tyrolian Alps are thereby regarded an increasingly popular destination for tourists seeking cooler climate in hot summer months (TI8). Increasing temperatures and longer summer seasons are thus as much interpreted as an opportunity for economic development as they are considered a threat (TD1).

Regarding the more informal *rules of the game*, two main things become apparent that point to a specific transformative governance culture in Tyrol: First, adaptation governance is based on a well-established governance approach, whereby local actors take responsibility for driving

interventions on the community level based on trust and informal approaches. These actors' knowledge of place and people's sentiments towards policy objectives like adaptation enable the formation of strategic coalitions for putting concrete projects on the ground (TI5). Second, well-established approaches in regional development and natural hazard management have given rise to a specific interpretation of the human-nature relationship that is also reflected in adaptation governance. Ensuring prosperity through economic development and, relatedly, protecting a modern cultural landscape characterized by agriculture and tourism from negative influences and, thereby, maintaining an established economic path for prosperity is a top priority. This is also reflected in the observation that adaptation is relatively uncontroversial in forestry, while it is shaped by conflict in tourism (TI1b). Similarly, it can be observed that the political approach to adaptation relies on the 'power of the market economy' (TI3) and tends to shift responsibility to individual behavioural change (TI6), whereas top-down decisions towards transformative change seem unconventional to say the least.

In summary, adaptation governance in Tyrol reveals several idiosyncrasies that can be attributed to a routinised governance culture – from the primacy of economic objectives in regional governance discourse to the delegation of responsibilities to the local level as a proven approach. In consequence, the set framework for spatial transformations primarily is to preserve the regional cultural landscape with its established, unsustainable land use patterns in the interests of regional identity and economy.

Lapland

Finnish Sápmi, or Lapland, is located in the northern Fennoscandia and mostly comprised of forests, fells and peatlands. As most of the province is located north of the Arctic Circle, Lapland experiences a faster warming than more southern latitudes (Markkula et al., 2019). According to the Lapland Climate Strategy 2030, expected climate impacts include an increase in mean temperature, number of hot days and weather anomalies such as heavy precipitation, while the number of frosty days and snow and ice cover are expected to decrease (Lapland Regional Council, 2011). The warming trend does not only impact the northern ecosystems, but also has severe consequences for agriculture, forestry, human health and infrastructure (Kivinen et al., 2017). As the ecosystems at risk are also cultural landscapes to the indigenous communities of the Sámi, alterations through climate change will “erode cultural meanings, stories, memories and traditional knowledge” (Markkula et al., 2019, p. 1080), affect traditional livelihoods such as hunting, fishing, harvesting, and reindeer herding (Kivinen et al., 2017; Axelsson-Linkowski et al., 2020; Moen et al., 2022), and nature-based tourism, which is an important provider of income and work for Sámi and Finnish inhabitants (Tervo-Kankare et al., 2018). Adapting these

livelihoods requires transformative governance approaches that acknowledge existing local knowledge and recognize regional differences (Rasmus et al., 2020, 2021).

Competencies for adaptation in Lapland lie at the national and regional level. The Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry coordinates adaptation strategies and action plans and the regional councils have political authority over certain sectors of action, while their scope of influence is limited, as Finland is a centralised state. The Regional Council of Lapland therefore has the political authority to implement certain adaptation measures, especially in the context of regional planning, but is dependent on national legislation and (inter-)national financing (LD2). The state's administrative agencies for regional management are important as well, as they are the biggest landowners, responsible for the management and maintenance of natural areas (LD2; LI1; LI5; LI6). Additionally, the Sámi Parliament – the primary political institution representing Sámi interests – completes the region's governance structure. However, the Sámi Parliament's role remains subordinate to the Finnish Parliament, with limited authority over land rights and self-governance (Kuokkanen, 2024).

The constellation of *actors* therefore results from the respective legal responsibilities: Key actors are the responsible ministry, the Regional Council of Lapland, the state's administrative agencies and the Sámi Parliament. Beyond that, research institutes and universities are as well affiliated with regional CCA, as their inclusion and cooperation have a great tradition not only in Lapland (LI5; LI6) but in the whole of Finland. Additionally, both Sámi and South Lapland reindeer herders' associations and cooperatives (LI1) act as "guidance actors" (LI5), steering reindeer research, expertise and economy and thus contributing to shape the discourse on the reindeer sector. However, an adequate institutional representation of the independent communities is still missing and the relationship between Finnish authorities and Sámi communities is tense (LI8).

As concerns *resources*, Finland can draw on an enormous repertoire of adaptation knowledge based on its pioneering role in adaptation planning in comparison to other EU countries. At the same time, the country profits from a well-maintained and well-functioning infrastructure, government, administration and societal service system (LD1, p. 27). However, these resources hardly reach as far north as Lapland. In fact, the region lacks human resources, funding for adaptation actions, a clear share of responsibilities and political prioritisation, e.g. of adaptation strategies (LI3; LI6; LI7; LI8): "We know that it's important, but [...] we don't have the resources, we don't have the money, we don't have the people and we don't have the time" (LI7). Generally, adaptation resources are scarce, and the Regional Council is dependent on the will of national administrative and academic institutions to cooperate and share resources (LI1; LI4; LI5; LI8). Consequently, a strong partnership between policymakers and researchers has

emerged, focusing on initiatives for CCA. Lapland is well advanced with conducting CCA projects derived from the cooperation with academia, which has tackled adaptation for 20 years and is profiting from a successful dialogue with local reindeer herders (LI5). Additionally, traditional and local knowledge from Sámi and Lappish communities serve as a significant resource in these efforts.

In terms of adaptation *discourse*, there are no dedicated adaptation documents for Lapland. Hence, the national CCA Plan (LD1) points the way forward. The national strategic vision on “Wellbeing, safety and security in a changing climate” (LD1, p.43) is however reflected by the regional aim for an enhanced resilience. Nevertheless, official documents make no statement on adaptation on the regional level, which is why the adaptation debate is very much characterised by informal rules, frames and visions. Additionally, although climate change in Lapland is accompanied also by positively perceived changes towards an increase in snow that is essential for winter tourism (LI2; LI7) and an extension of the vegetation period (LI9), in general, more pessimistic outlooks towards expected irreversible changes prevail (LI1; LI3, LI8). For example, for reindeer herding, the discussion on climate impacts increasingly shifted from winter season, for which coping mechanisms have already been developed by local herders, to summer season, entailing new challenges such as long heat periods, new kinds of insects and diseases (LI5).

As concerns the *rules of the game*, regional governance as such is fundamentally shaped by the region’s identity – its multiculturalism, remoteness, distinct arctic climate and, thus, the connection and economic and cultural dependency on specific conditions of nature (LI1; LI5). This also significantly shapes the approaches to and understanding of adaptation, with the latter fluctuating between adaptation as transformative change in every sector (LI2; LI8) and adaptation as preservation of regional economies (LVDWS). However, there has long been a simmering conflict between traditional livelihoods and modern tourism development – particularly regarding land use – that is becoming more apparent now in the face of climate change. Yet, there is a common awareness among the groups representing these competing interests and visions that this issue must be reconciled to properly address adaptation issues. For the indigenous Sámi communities, reindeer herding and other livelihoods are both an economic factor and transgenerational cultural value (LI8). To preserve this way of life, traditional livelihoods are thus specifically emphasised in adaptation governance (LI5) and the formal and informal standing and inclusion of the Sámi play a big role. In consequence, livelihood-specific adaptation strategies that are equally based on scientific and traditional knowledge are being envisioned (LI4; LI5; LI9). Overall, practicality plays a key role in adaptation in Lapland (LI1), explaining why implementation is prioritised over strategy development on the issue (LI7).

However, the absence of regional strategies has implications on the directionality of adaptation governance and the implementation of transformative activities (LI4).

Consequently, the fragmented governance and lack of overarching strategies result in fragmentation of adaptation (LI1), where individual stakeholders “are challenged to decide whether they need their own adaptation plan” (LI5). The influence of a specific governance culture on adaptation governance and spatial transformations in Lapland is already evident in the deeply rooted conflict between tradition and modernity. Divergent ideas about the general economic development of the region and very specific land use questions are already an integral part of the region's material and cultural governance arrangements. The challenge of climate change only amplifies this as a specific trait of a regional transformative governance culture that needs to be dealt with.

Râu Sadului/Sibiu

Râu Sadului is a commune in Sibiu County, part of the region Mărginimea Sibiului, located between the Cindrel Mountains and Transylvanian hills. The area is defined by a mountainous landscape with hills and plateaus, and a depression zone vital for agriculture (Coroş et al., 2021; Adamov et al., 2022). Since 1989, the region diversified its economic activities into traditional crafts, food processing, and tourism. Boosted by Sibiu's status as 2007 European Cultural Capital, tourism began to boom and became a significant source of income, exemplified by the region's doubling number in arrivals between 2007-2016 (Brătucu et al., 2017; Adamov et al., 2022). Sibiu's regional identity is deeply rooted in its vibrant customs and traditions. Its agricultural heritage – being known as the “most famous pastoral sheepherding region for sheep's cheese” (RI4) in Romania – factors into that, while increasingly modern opportunities like ecotourism and agrotourism are being sought. The looming increase in mean temperature and heat waves, droughts and heavy precipitation events is not only expected to have direct impacts on local, mostly rural tourism (Velea et al., 2024), but also on agriculture, forestry, and food production (Prăvălie et al., 2020), as droughts are considered a key challenge for crop-production in Romania (Ministry of Environment, 2017).

Formally, responsibility for climate adaptation in Romania is distributed among different national, regional and local levels. Based on the existing administrative-territorial structure of Sibiu County, there are two levels of competences with counties in the upper level, and towns and communes (groups of villages) in the lower level (Benedek & Bajtalan, 2015). Based on Romania's Constitution, the County gained central decision-making and implementation competencies in many fields of relevance for CCA in 1991. However, central and national authorities still retain significant control over regional governance through a strong top-down

mentality that is generally recognisable in policy and implementation processes (Dumitrică, 2011).

The *actor* landscape in adaptation governance is diverse, consisting of ministries, regional and local councils, park authorities, universities and research institutes, farmer associations, and businesses, but also water and tourism associations, civic organisations, community associations and NGOs. Sibiu County Council plays a pivotal role due to its authority over financial distribution and policy implementation, surpassing the powers of local authorities such as the City Hall (RI2). Also, municipalities, especially medium-sized and larger ones, act as important multipliers to ensure adaptation strategies at the local level (RI3). However, scarce resources and a lack of collaboration often put institutions in competition (RI2).

Budgetary constraints and lacking know-how characterise the *resource* dimension of adaptation governance in Râu Sadului. With resource management issues compounding these challenges, funding shortfalls of soft adaptation measures, like training or awareness building, are common. However, present regional adaptation actions reflect essential skills in successful acquisition of EU funding. EU-funded projects have thus largely served as critical enablers for regional climate action (RI3). This is also reflected in the municipality's early regional adaptation activities that have also enabled the development of human capacities and expert knowledge to address CCA on regional level.

In terms of adaptation *discourse*, Romania has produced several national strategies on CCA, particularly since 2022, such as the National Action Plan for Implementing Climate Adaptation (RD1) and the National Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change (RD2). Also at the regional scale, Sibiu proposed a Strategy and Plan for Mitigating and Adapting to Climate Change (RD5) and a best practice guide for Sibiu County Council (RD) to support adaptation action. In general, leading documents take a dominant focus towards combatting climate hazards, with priorities being laid on reducing the impact of climate change on agriculture, rural development, water and infrastructure (RD3; RD4; RD6). Strategic national documents thus point out the need to protect “environment, people and economic activities from climate change”, emphasising risk reduction and the mainstreaming of climate policies and actions into smart, green, inclusive, and growth-oriented strategies (RD3). Regional programs rather emphasise sectoral priorities, such as water management, reforestation and expanding green spaces, while often positioning climate adaptation as a secondary goal behind economic interests (RI3). However, adaptation strategies do also target soft measures such as knowledge exchange or training in local communities as key for successful adaptation. Yet, these are often met with distrust in relation to traditional, technologically or economically oriented approaches (RI2).

This is further echoed by the *informal rules* of regional adaptation governance. For one, public-private collaborations are generally considered most fruitful in regional governance and are hence also emphasised as the “best scenario” (RI2) for addressing regional adaptation needs and driving local action. As a result, however, many adaptation projects are guided and legitimised through economic objectives, e.g., promoting touristic activities in the region (RI3). In consequence, local businesses – particularly regional farmers’ associations – exert significant power and influence on agenda setting, sometimes sidelining ecological perspectives for economic benefits (RI2). In the face of the region’s ongoing demographic decline, a focus towards functioning local economies and income opportunities seems logical to sustain rural populations and prevent outmigration to urban centres. At the same time, being closely tied to national financial allocations and priority settings, local authorities also tend to show inertia in decision-making, being plagued by instability and bureaucratic indecisions (Talmaciu, 2014; Văidianu et al., 2020), which complicates a strategic approach to regional adaptation governance. Hence, there is a perception of a need for “simple, cheap solutions” (RI4) in CCA that prioritise economic practicality over ecological strategy. Such pragmatism and informality are also reinforced by governance fragmentation and a rather tokenistic stakeholder involvement. Limited participation hampers the effectiveness of regional interventions and leads to a dominance of economic interest groups (RI2). This is further fuelled by an overall insufficient problem awareness and limited acceptance of CCA measures among key governance actors in the region (RI3; RI4; RI5).

Hence, in Râu Sadului, too, it becomes clear how routinised governance practices and deep-seated values associated with the region and “beneficial” regional policy influence regional transformative governance. The region reveals an ambivalence between a discursive proactivity and openness to embrace innovative solutions, and the cumbersome implementation, cooperation and communication among the many involved actors in practice. Despite unanimous recognition of the pressing need for adaptation, economic scarcity, fragmented governance and contradictory legislative frameworks continue to hinder coordinated action. The consequence in terms of spatial transformations is an incoherent planning and conflicting actions in the management of forests, grasslands, and water systems, as well as the development of rural tourism and agriculture (RI2). Concerning transformative climate action, the goal of economic viability that is represented by an established regional development regime outdoes the objectives of an emerging regional adaptation governance configuration. At best, adaptation can hence be legitimized by its contribution to the continuation of a traditional economic development path, hence jeopardising transformative change.

Table 2 – Overview of key aspects determining CCA policy arrangements in the three case study regions

	Tyrol	Lapland	Râu Sadului
Key actors involved	Municipalities, intermediary KLAR! managers, interest groups from agriculture and tourism, semi-public organisations	National authorities, administrative agencies, Regional Council, Sámi Parliament, reindeer herders, research institutes	National authorities, Sibiu County Council, large municipalities, businesses, universities, NGOs, agricultural, water and tourism associations
Relevant resources leveraged	Solid financial base at regional level vs. constrained municipal budgets; CCA governance benefits from hazard management expertise	Expertise on national level; scientific partnerships and traditional knowledge; shortage of regional funding and human capacity	Limited local capacities; EU funds are critical for capacity building, strategy development, and implementation
Dominant discursive framings	Dominated by touristic self-image and preservation of cultural landscape; opportunity-oriented tone	Lack of directionality and vision; dominated by conditions of nature, reindeer herding, and Sámi culture	Prioritisation of regional CCA needs; economic pressure typically outduels “soft” CCA; call for “simple” solutions
Rules of the game	Informal, trust-based governance; governance issues are being delegated to the local level	Ambivalence of tradition and modernity / preservation and transformation; pragmatic stance towards governance	Preference for PPPs; business interests are a priority in the face of scarcity and shrinkage, thus needed to legitimise CCA

Discussion

Our analysis indicates that while CCA has visibly entered policy and practice debates in European mountain regions, the primary motivator for adaptation in all three of our case studies was economic vulnerability. In Tyrol, it was even referred to as “the main lever for driving adaptation action” (T17). On a strategic level, there was a clear tendency of interpreting adaptation as a means to sustaining established regional economic growth paths. This is in line with recent findings on the role of mitigation approaches in the context of regional economic development (cf. Chlebna & Suitner, 2025). Hence, while regional economies in our cases did act as catalysts of (incremental) adaptation, paradoxically, the maintenance of sectors that are deemed key to both prosperity and identity, at the same time poses a major barrier to transformative change in these sectors and related spatial configurations.

Discourse played an important part in establishing such conceptions. The connection between a unique cultural landscape shaped by agriculture, tourism, and traditions-oriented lifestyles, and an associated regional economy and regional identity is repeatedly emphasised. This framing significantly restricts spatial transformations from the outset, as they would hence be considered massive interventions in the region's wealth and values. While the concrete

framings differ between regions, these findings still point to the influence of narratives, frames, and imaginaries on regional CCA (cf. Milkoreit, 2017; Olazabal et al., 2024; Kanarp et al., 2025). Conversely, this points to the relevance of regional discourse, especially jointly developed inclusive visions of a climate-resilient regional future as a lever of transformative climate governance.

A closer look at each region shows nuances in how economic development and climate change adaptation are being negotiated and approached. In Tyrol, public discourse portrays CCA as an economic opportunity for the region, aiming to legitimise interventions and investments oriented at CCA that way. On a more informal level, decisionmakers are well aware that CCA is a necessity, however one that requires particular sensitivity vis-à-vis dominant economic stakeholders and a general public. This reflects a governance culture that favours informal cooperation, familiar development models (e.g., with a strong tourism-orientation), and incremental change. In Lapland, adaptation discourse is shaped by administrative institutions, the Sámi Parliament, and reindeer herding communities. Here, climate governance is closely tied to cultural identity and traditional practices as part of the economic development perspective. But it remains loosely coordinated due to the absence of a guiding strategy – indicating a pragmatic but fragmented governance setting. In Râu Sadului, economic growth is prioritised, driven by regional authorities' dependence on external funding. Despite multiple actors being involved, weak collaboration and limited capacity lead to a fragmented adaptation approach shaped more by practical constraints than strategic vision.

In all three regions, there are only insufficient strategic adaptation frameworks to guide targeted activities. This makes concerted action difficult because there is no clarity about roles and responsibilities, the spatial and lifeworldly implications, or the transformative future goals to be achieved. As a result, adaptation actions often remain fragmented, driven by different interest groups, and dependent on the provision of resources from (supra-)national levels. This can be interpreted either as a shortcoming in regional governance or as a consequence of the difficult-to-navigate multi-level dynamics in regional CCA governance. As described above, regions such as Râu Sadului are economically dependent on transnational institutions that allocate the resources necessary for implementing CCA. Only affluent regions like Tyrol and Lapland can afford more leeway. However, all three are embedded in their respective national contexts that top-down define individual but insufficiently specific expectations and frameworks for the regional implementation of CCA. Conversely, established regional governance approaches, such as well-proven cooperation modes with local actors, constitute a certain path-dependency that can't be passed over easily. Hence, regional CCA governance becomes a trial-and-error approach driven by experience and expectations.

Also, (supra-)national strategies and funding often lack regional differentiation that would be needed to match actual regional adaptation abilities. With that, also the embeddedness of local perceptions, needs and knowledge is often neglected, while being essential for effective, efficient, and accepted regional measures (as is emphasised for instance by Hanssen et al., 2013; Rasmus et al., 2020, 2021). In this regard, the case of Lapland illustrates the importance of incorporating indigenous perspectives on nature into mainstream transformative regional development concepts. While still remaining underrepresented in adaptation literature (cf. Wilson et al., 2022), Sámi traditional knowledge offers place-based insights that can enhance resilience strategies when properly integrated (Okedele et al., 2024). The establishment of the Sámi Climate Council in Finland in 2023 marks an important institutional step toward anchoring these perspectives in national climate policy (LI9; Kimura, 2024). To move from symbolic inclusion to transformative change, governance structures, however, need to shift from indigenous participation to indigenous-led processes – supported by boundary organisations, inclusive mechanisms such as truth-telling and capacity-building, and reflexive, co-designed approaches like collaborative action research between Sámi communities and national authorities (Zurba, 2023; Larsen et al., 2017), while respecting the legal distinction between indigenous and local communities (Kimura, 2024).

Beyond that, the influence of regional governance idiosyncrasies on specific adaptation approaches becomes obvious. While region-specific climate hazards and impacts are still the main factor determining regional adaptation strategy and action, the “how” and “why” largely depends on other factors. On the one hand, these are the formal competencies and resources with which the regions are equipped to carry out autonomous adaptation governance. On the other hand, it is the existence of well-established informal regional development regimes constituted by a specific configuration of regional stakeholders who – quite naturally – take the lead in emerging fields of relevance for regional governance, such as CCA. This is directly linked to deeply rooted conceptions of regional decision-making, established governance routines, values and beliefs, i.e., the informal rules of the game. In Tyrol, this includes the seemingly natural delegation of responsibility for CCA to KLAR!-managers and, hence, the municipal and community level, as well as the imaginary of protecting any human activities from nature’s destructive force. In Lapland and Râu Sadului, it points to the prioritisation of pragmatic solutions over strategic frameworks. In Lapland, it further involves the integration of indigenous knowledge into regional governance decisions, and in Râu Sadului the look into routines and traditions of governing regional stability and change helps explain the primacy of economic objectives in regional adaptation governance.

The fact that differences in regional climate change responses are not exclusively due to regionally different climate change impacts thus underlines the findings of other research that has already pointed to regional differences in governance structures as influencing factors of regional variation in CCA (cf. Birchall et al., 2023, among others). However, our case studies have shown that, in addition to these structural influences, there are also cultural variations stemming from place-bound framings, routines, and self-conceptions of “doing” regional governance – similar to those discussed in the planning cultures literature (cf. Othengrafen and Reimer, 2013, among others). We hence contend that such entrenched cultures of regional climate governance should be considered more in both regional climate governance research and practice. Our results also reveal that while governance cultures vary across regions, commonalities such as struggles with multi-level governance and adaptation policy’s rooting in localised approaches still exist. It will thus be interesting to further observe the different dynamics that macro-regional strategies oriented at climate policy will induce on the regional level (cf. for instance Cattivelli, 2023) and to study how cultural traits mediate regional adaptive capacity and resilience in specific areas of intervention.

Conclusion

Despite a recognition that place-bound cultural factors have essential influence on adaptation pathways and regional governance responses, studies addressing the influence of region-specific modes of *doing* governance on concrete actions and spatial transformations remain limited. In this article, we examined CCA governance in three European mountain regions with a policy arrangements approach to underscore the role of place-bound transformative governance cultures in the formation of variegated climate change responses. The analysis revealed how regional governance idiosyncrasies influenced CCA governance. Aside from influential structural and material factors such as formal competencies and financial resources, this became evident from the actor constellations. They rather represented well-tested trust- and experience-based coalitions from regional governance endeavours in other areas than expertise- and capacity-driven compositions oriented specifically at regional CCA. Informal rules also played a significant part, explaining why a municipal perspective (Tyrol), pragmatism (Lapland), or local business-orientation (Râu Sadului) “naturally” shaped CCA governance in the respective regions. Moreover, adaptation discourse unveiled that addressing region-specific climate impacts must be made meaningful vis-à-vis the respective framings of a regional development path.

Such findings put widely emphasised climate governance tools like climate policy mainstreaming into question, as adaptation measures continue to be influenced by cultural

factors. We believe that this necessitates regional strategies that better integrate place-based ecological *and* cultural assets. That said, our analysis revealed that at the time being our cases did not have dedicated regional risk or vulnerability assessments. CCA efforts instead mainly relied on national- or regional-level projections, occasional assessments on isolated issues, and existing resources and capacities within the respective policy arrangement. Activities were hence lacking a comprehensive evidence-based foundation, running the risk of jeopardising the intended impact. While this is a call for comprehensive risk and vulnerability assessments on regional level, this observation also illustrates how the design of transformational activities is as much a question of climatic and socio-economic analysis, as of socio-political negotiation and socio-cultural embedding.

As with any research, there are limitations inherent in this study. First, as concerns case study selection, we have stated above that our decision was a compromise between taking a multi-case approach to address regional variation in governance responses and satisfactory availability and accessibility of relevant data for each case. With this came certain trade-offs concerning the comparability of regions, particularly regarding different governance contexts and variability in hazards and impacts. As for the first issue, we were able to show that despite structural differences, the cultural dimension of regional governance had visible influence on CCA responses in each case. Yet, we also considered the structural dimension less, while it certainly offers additional explanatory value for variation in regional CCA and should hence also be studied more (cf. for instance Birchall et al., 2023). As for the latter, we prioritised comparability of affected key sectors (i.e., agriculture and tourism) over comparability of hazards and impacts. Both are of course important. As it was not possible though to find regions where the same sectors were of comparable significance to the regions and threatened by the same hazards and impacts, while also providing data of sufficient quality to examine the respective policy arrangements, we ultimately went for a sectoral perspective while attaching less importance to hazards and impacts. We do not believe that this fundamentally undermines the integrity of our results, as this focus unveiled the influence of historically evolved regional policy arrangements on CCA. However, we want to emphasize that more comparative research on the issue is needed – not only with a focus on other sectors, but specifically between regions with comparable hazards and impacts.

Concerning the data, the identification of pertinent policy documents and the selection of suitable interviewees and workshop participants was a joint effort of us (as external researchers) and our regional project partners (as knowledgeable locals). That way, both theoretical and methodological considerations as well as experiential knowledge were incorporated into the selection process. While, often enough, only our local partners' networks and tacit knowledge

made access to relevant materials and actors even possible, it cannot be completely ruled out that a certain bias among partners may have affected this process and the course of the analysis. Furthermore, while online interviews and workshops – as opposed to meeting face-to-face – enabled broader participation in dispersed mountainous regions, it should not be overlooked that language and digital skills were potential barriers with an exclusionary effect. Lastly, while we have been able to unveil relevant aspects in all four policy arrangement dimensions, the “rules of the game” have proven to be particularly hard to uncover. This is certainly due to our methodological approach. It is inherently difficult to assess the informal norms, routines, and logics subsumed under this category through policy documents, interviews, and workshops. While our study has brought certain points to light, this category might still appear underexplored compared to the others. This hints at the relevance of ethnographic fieldwork, long-term participant observation, shadowing techniques, and other similar methods to better uncover the implicit values and practices informing regional governance cultures.

To conclude, we encourage further research on the cultural dimension of transformative governance to make sense of regional variability beyond regional structural features and varying climate hazards and impacts. We are convinced that this will also enable the development of more fitting and accepted approaches to the necessary regional spatial transformations provoked by transformative climate governance strategies.

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Conflict of interest

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References

- Abegg, B., Agrawala, S., Crick, F., & de Montfalcon, A. (2007). Climate change impacts and adaptation in winter tourism. In S. Agrawala (Ed.), *Climate Change in the European Alps: Adapting Winter Tourism and Natural Hazards Management* (pp. 25–60). OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264031692-en>
- Adamov, T., Iancu, T., Peș, E., Popescu, G., Șmuleac, L., Feher, A., & Ciolac, R. (2022). Rural Tourism in Marginimea Sibiului Area—A Possibility of Capitalizing on Local Resources. *Sustainability*, 15(1), 241. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15010241>
- Adger, W. N., Barnett, J., Brown, K., Marshall, N., & O’Brien, K. (2013). Cultural dimensions of climate change impacts and adaptation. *Nature Climate Change*, 3(2), 112–117. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate1666>
- Aguiar, F. C., Bentz, J., Silva, J. M. N., Fonseca, A. L., Swart, R., Santos, F. D., & Penha-Lopes, G. (2018). Adaptation to climate change at local level in Europe: An overview. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 86, 38–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2018.04.010>
- Alberton, M., Bußjäger, P., Meier, A., & Parolari, S. (2022). Climate Change at Subnational Level: The Case Study of the Autonomous Provinces of Trento and Bolzano (Italy) and the Länder Tyrol and Vorarlberg (Austria). In *Climate Change Integration in the Multilevel Governance of Italy and Austria* (pp. 68–92). Brill Nijhoff. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004513006_005
- Amundsen, H., Berglund, F., & Westskog, H. (2010). Overcoming Barriers to Climate Change Adaptation—A Question of Multilevel Governance? *Environment and Planning C: Government and Policy*, 28(2), 276–289. <https://doi.org/10.1068/c0941>

- Arts, B., Leroy, P., & Van Tatenhove, J. (2006). Political Modernisation and Policy Arrangements: A Framework for Understanding Environmental Policy Change. *Public Organization Review*, 6(2), 93–106. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11115-006-0001-4>
- Arts, B., & Van Tatenhove, J. (2000). Environmental Policy Arrangements: A New Concept. In H. Goverde (Ed.), *Global and European Polity?: Organisations, Policies, Contexts: Organisations, Policies, Contexts*. Routledge.
- Arts, B., & Van Tatenhove, J. (2004). Policy and power: A conceptual framework between the 'old' and 'new' policy idioms. *Policy Sciences*, 37(3), 339–356. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11077-005-0156-9>
- Axelsson-Linkowski, W., Fjellström, A.-M., Sandström, C., Westin, A., Östlund, L., & Moen, J. (2020). Shifting Strategies between Generations in Sami Reindeer Husbandry: The Challenges of Maintaining Traditions while Adapting to a Changing Context. *Human Ecology*, 48(4), 481–490. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10745-020-00171-3>
- Barnett, J., Graham, S., Quinn, T., Adger, W. N., & Butler, C. (2021). Three ways social identity shapes climate change adaptation. *Environmental Research Letters*, 16(12), 124029. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac36f7>
- Bauer, A., & Steurer, R. (2014). Multi-level governance of climate change adaptation through regional partnerships in Canada and England. *Geoforum*, 51, 121–129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2013.10.006>
- Benedek, J., & Bajtalan, H. (2015). Recent regionalization discourses and projects in Romania with special focus on the Székelyland. *Transylvanian Review of Administrative Sciences*, 11(44), 23–41.
- Benz, A., & Eberlein, B. (1999). The Europeanization of regional policies: patterns of multi-level governance. *Journal of European public policy*, 6(2), 329–348.
- Benzie, M., & Persson, Å. (2019). Governing borderless climate risks: Moving beyond the territorial framing of adaptation. *International Environmental Agreements: Politics, Law and Economics*, 19(4), 369–393. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10784-019-09441-y>
- Biesbroek, G. R., Swart, R. J., Carter, T. R., Cowan, C., Henrichs, T., Mela, H., Morecroft, M. D., & Rey, D. (2010). Europe adapts to climate change: Comparing National Adaptation Strategies. *Global Environmental Change*, 20(3), 440–450. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2010.03.005>
- Birchall, S. J., Bonnett, N., & Kehler, S. (2023). The influence of governance structure on local resilience: Enabling and constraining factors for climate change adaptation in practice. *Urban Climate*, 47, 101348.
- Bogner, A., Littig, B., & Menz, W. (2009). *Interviewing experts*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Bonnett, N. L., & Birchall, S. J. (2023). The influence of regional strategic policy on municipal climate adaptation planning. *Regional Studies*, 57(1), 141–152. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00343404.2022.2049224>
- Brătucu, G., Băltescu, C. A., Neacșu, N. A., Boșcor, D., Țierean, O. M., & Madar, A. (2017). Approaching the Sustainable Development Practices in Mountain Tourism in the Romanian Carpathians. *Sustainability*, 9(11), 2051. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9112051>
- Brunetti, M., Lentini, G., Maugeri, M., Nanni, T., Auer, I., Böhm, R., & Schöner, W. (2009). Climate variability and change in the Greater Alpine Region over the last two centuries based on multi-variable analysis. *International Journal of Climatology*, 29, 2197–2225. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.1857>
- Buijs, A., Hansen, R., Van der Jagt, S., Ambrose-Oji, B., Elands, B., Lorange Rall, E., Mattijssen, T., Pauleit, S., Runhaar, H., Stahl Olafsson, A., & Steen Møller, M. (2019). Mosaic governance for urban green infrastructure: Upscaling active citizenship from a local

- government perspective. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 40, 53–62.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2018.06.011>
- Cattivelli, V. (2023). Macro-Regional Strategies, Climate Policies and Regional Climatic Governance in the Alps. *Climate*, 11(2), 37. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cli11020037>
- Chaffin, B. C., Garmestani, A. S., Gunderson, L. H., Benson, M. H., Angeler, D. G., Arnold, C. A. (Tony), Cosens, B., Craig, R. K., Ruhl, J. B., & Allen, C. R. (2016). Transformative Environmental Governance. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 41(1), 399–423. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-110615-085817>
- Chimani, B., Heinrich, G., Hofstätter, M., Kerschbaumer, M., Kienberger, S., Leuprecht, A., Lexer, A., Peßenteiner, S., Poetsch, M., Salzmann, M., Spiekermann, R., Switanek, M., & Truhetz, H. (2016). *Kimaszenarien für das Bundesland Tirol bis 2100*.
- Christopoulos, D. C. (2006). Governance Capacity and Regionalist Dynamics. *Regional & Federal Studies*, 16(4), 363–383. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13597560600988997>
- Contesse, M., van Vliet, B. J. M., & Lenhart, J. (2018). Is urban agriculture urban green space? A comparison of policy arrangements for urban green space and urban agriculture in Santiago de Chile. *Land Use Policy*, 71, 566–577.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2017.11.006>
- Coroş, M. M., Privitera, D., Păunescu, L. M., Nedelcu, A., Lupu, C., & Ganuşceac, A. (2021). Mărginimea Sibiului Tells Its Story: Sustainability, Cultural Heritage and Rural Tourism—A Supply-Side Perspective. *Sustainability*, 13(9), 5309.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su13095309>
- Dannevig, H., & Aall, C. (2015). The regional level as boundary organization? An analysis of climate change adaptation governance in Norway. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 54, 168–175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2015.07.001>
- Directorate-General for Climate Action. (n.d.). *EU Adaptation Strategy*. European Commission. Retrieved 14 October 2024, from https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/adaptation-climate-change/eu-adaptation-strategy_en
- Dumitrică, C. D. (2011). The Future of Public Administration in Romania Between Centralization and Decentralization. *Paper published in the Presented Papers from the 19th NISPAcece Annual Conferences* May 19-22, 2011, Varna, Bulgaria.
- Ensor, J., & Berger, R. (2009). Community-based adaptation and culture in theory and practice. In *Adapting to climate change: Thresholds, values, governance* (pp. 227–239).
https://unfccc.int/files/adaptation/application/pdf/nwpexpert_ensor_berger_2009.pdf
- Eriksen, S. H., Nightingale, A. J., & Eakin, H. (2015). Reframing adaptation: The political nature of climate change adaptation. *Global Environmental Change*, 35, 523–533.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2015.09.014>
- Eurostat. (2022). Regional gross domestic product (PPS per inhabitant) by NUTS 2 regions [Dataset].
https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tgs00005/default/table?lang=en&category=t_reg.t_reg_eco
- Fedele, G., Donatti, C. I., Harvey, C. A., Hannah, L., & Hole, D. G. (2019). Transformative adaptation to climate change for sustainable social-ecological systems. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 101, 116–125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2019.07.001>
- Filho, W. L., Salvia, A. L., Balogun, A.-L., Pereira, M. J. V., Mucova, S. A. R., Ajulo, O. M., Ng, A., Gwenzi, J., Mashonjowa, E., Aina, Y. A., Li, C., Totin, E., Pinho, P., Campbell, D., Chanza, N., & Setti, A. F. F. (2023). Towards more sustainable responses to natural hazards and climate change challenges via transformative adaptation. *Cities*, 141, 104525.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2023.104525>

- Finnish Government. (2024). *Government Report on Finland's National Climate Change Adaptation Plan until 2030. Wellbeing, Safety and Security in a Changing Climate*. https://julkaisut.valtioneuvosto.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/165528/VN_2024_11.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y
- Fresque-Baxter, J. A., & Armitage, D. (2012). Place identity and climate change adaptation: A synthesis and framework for understanding. *WIREs Climate Change*, 3(3), 251–266. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.164>
- Gorddard, R., Colloff, M. J., Wise, R. M., Ware, D., & Dunlop, M. (2016). Values, rules and knowledge: Adaptation as change in the decision context. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 57, 60–69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2015.12.004>
- Granberg, M., Bosomworth, K., Moloney, S., Kristianssen, A.-C., & Fünfgeld, H. (2019a). Can Regional-Scale Governance and Planning Support Transformative Adaptation? A Study of Two Places. *Sustainability*, 11(24), Article 24. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11246978>
- Granberg, M., Bosomworth, K., Moloney, S., Kristianssen, A.-C., & Fünfgeld, H. (2019b). Can Regional-Scale Governance and Planning Support Transformative Adaptation? A Study of Two Places. *Sustainability*, 11(24), 6978. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11246978>
- Gupta, J. (2007). *The multi-level governance challenge of climate change*. *Environmental Sciences*, 4(3), 131-137.
- Hansen, G. S., Mydske, P. K., & Dahle, E. (2013). Multi-level coordination of climate change adaptation: By national hierarchical steering or by regional network governance? *Local Environment*, 18(8), 869–887. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2012.738657>
- Hohenwallner, D., Anderl, M., Bürgel, J., Goler, R., Hama, M., Huber, T., Ibesich, N., Kratzer, A., Krutzler, T., Lampert, C., Leitner, M., Link, S., Nagl, C., Rigler, E., Schmid, C., Schneider, J., Schieder, W., Schröer, K., Schwab, K., ... Zethner, G. (2015). *Sachstandbericht Klimawandel in Tirol*.
- Hooghe, L., & Marks, G. (2003). Unraveling the central state, but how? Types of multi-level governance. *American political science review*, 97(2), 233-243.
- Horcea-Milcu, A. I., Dorresteijn, I., Leventon, J., Stojanovic, M., Lam, D. P., Lang, D. J., & Zimmermann, S. (2024). Transformative research for sustainability: Characteristics, tensions, and moving forward. *Global Sustainability*, 7, e14.
- Ingold, K., Balsiger, J., & Hirschi, C. (2010). Climate change in mountain regions: How local communities adapt to extreme events. *Local Environment*, 15(7), 651–661. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2010.498811>
- IPCC. (2023). *Climate Change 2022 – Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability: Working Group II Contribution to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* (1st ed.). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009325844>
- Juhola, S., Haanpää, S., & Peltonen, L. (2012). Regional challenges of climate change adaptation in Finland: Examining the ability to adapt in the absence of national level steering. *Local Environment*, 17(6–7), 629–639. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2012.665860>
- Kalbach, J., Tippin, M., & Chin, D. (2018). *The Definitive Guide To Facilitating Remote Workshops: Insights, Tools, and Case Studies from Digital-first Companies and Expert Facilitators*. CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform.
- Kanarp, G. C. S., Böhm, S., & Löf, A. (2025). Contested adaptation futures: the role of global imaginaries in climate adaptation governance. *Sustainability Science*, 1-21.
- Kelemen, E., Subramanian, S. M., De Vos, A., Amaruzaman, S., Porter-Bolland, L., Islar, M., Kosmus, M., Nakangu, B., Nuesiri, E., Robles, G. A., Yiu, E., Emerton, L., & Zólyomi, Á. (2023). Signposts on the road toward transformative governance: How a stronger focus

- on diverse values can enhance environmental policies. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 64, 101351.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2023.101351>
- Khan, M. R., & Roberts, J. T. (2013). Adaptation and international climate policy. *WIREs Climate Change*, 4(3), 171–189. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.212>
- Kivinen, S., Rasmus, S., Jylhä, K., & Laapas, M. (2017). Long-Term Climate Trends and Extreme Events in Northern Fennoscandia (1914-2013). *Climate*, 5(1), 16.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/cli5010016>
- Kimura, H. (2024). Differentiating Indigenous Peoples from local communities under climate regimes in just energy transition: Implications for the Inuit and Sami Peoples. *Polar Science*, 101123.
- Klima- und Energiefonds. (2024). *KLAR! Regionen stellen sich den Folgen des Klimawandels*.
<https://klar-anpassungsregionen.at/>
- Kuokkanen, R. (2024). The problem of culturalizing indigenous self-determination: Sámi cultural autonomy in Finland. *The Polar Journal*, 14(1), 148–166.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/2154896X.2024.2342125>
- Landeshauptstadt Innsbruck, Amt für Verkehrsplanung, Umwelt (2020). *Strategie zur Anpassung an den Klimawandel in Innsbruck*. Retrieved 08 May 2025, from
https://www.innsbruck.gv.at/_Resources/Persistent/c3bc936235589e41c38d1e133c732508fc0cd889/strategie_zur_anpassung_an_den_klimawandel_gesamt.pdf
- Lachapelle, G., & Oñate, P. (2018). *Borders and margins: federalism, devolution and multi-level governance* (p. 300). Verlag Barbara Budrich.
- Lapland Regional Council (2011). *Lapland Climate Strategy 2030*. Retrieved 08 May 2025, from
<https://lapitoy.sharepoint.com/sites/Lapinliittojulkiset/Tiedostot/Forms/AllItems.aspx?id=%2Fsites%2FLapinliittojulkiset%2FTiedostot%2FMaakuntakaavat%2FLapin%20ilma%2Fstostrategia&p=true&ga=1>
- Larsen, R. K., Raitio, K., Stinnerbom, M., & Wik-Karlsson, J. (2017). Sami-state collaboration in the governance of cumulative effects assessment: A critical action research approach. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 64, 67-76.
- Lesnikowski, A., Ford, J., Biesbroek, R., Berrang-Ford, L., Maillet, M., Araos, M., & Austin, S. E. (2017). What does the Paris Agreement mean for adaptation? *Climate Policy*, 17(7), 825–831. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2016.1248889>
- Markkula, I., Turunen, M., & Rasmus, S. (2019). A review of climate change impacts on the ecosystem services in the Saami Homeland in Finland. *Science of The Total Environment*, 692, 1070–1085. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.07.272>
- Marks, D., Bayrak, M. M., Jahangir, S., Henig, D., & Bailey, A. (2022). Towards a cultural lens for adaptation pathways to climate change. *Regional Environmental Change*, 22(1), 22.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-022-01884-5>
- Marshall, N. A., Park, S. E., Adger, W. N., Brown, K., & Howden, S. M. (2012). Transformational capacity and the influence of place and identity. *Environmental Research Letters*, 7(3), 034022. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/7/3/034022>
- McDowell, G., Huggel, C., Frey, H., Wang, F. M., Cramer, K., & Ricciardi, V. (2019). Adaptation action and research in glaciated mountain systems: Are they enough to meet the challenge of climate change? *Global Environmental Change*, 54, 19–30.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2018.10.012>
- McNeeley, S. M., & Lazrus, H. (2014). The Cultural Theory of Risk for Climate Change Adaptation. *Weather, Climate, and Society*, 6(4), 506–519.
<https://doi.org/10.1175/WCAS-D-13-00027.1>

- Milkoreit, M. (2017). Imaginary politics: Climate change and making the future. *Elem Sci Anth*, 5, 62.
- Ministry of Environment (2017). *Romania's 7th National Communication under the United Nations Framework Convention on climate change*. Retrieved 08 May 2025, from https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/0587134_Romania-NC7-1-NC7_ROMANIA.pdf
- Moen, J., Holand, Ø., Kumpula, J., & Horstkotte, T. (2022). *Reindeer Husbandry and Global Environmental Change: Pastoralism in Fennoscandia* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003118565>
- Morrison, T. H. (2014). Developing a regional governance index: The institutional potential of rural regions. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 35, 101–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2014.04.004>
- MountResilience. (n.d.). Solutions for Resilient Communities in European Mountain Areas. MountResilience. Retrieved 26 August 2025, from <https://mountresilience.eu/>
- Nalau, J., Preston, B. L., & Maloney, M. C. (2015). Is adaptation a local responsibility? *Environmental Science & Policy*, 48, 89–98. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2014.12.011>
- Nolte, D. (2016). Regional governance from a comparative perspective. In *Economy, politics and governance challenges* (pp. 1–16). Nova Publishers.
- Olazabal, M., Amorim-Maia, A. T., Alda-Vidal, C., & Goodwin, S. (2024). What is limiting how we imagine climate change adaptation?. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 71, 101476.
- Othengrafen, F., & Reimer, M. (2013). The embeddedness of planning in cultural contexts: theoretical foundations for the analysis of dynamic planning cultures. *Environment and Planning A*, 45(6), 1269-1284.
- Pascual, U., McElwee, P. D., Diamond, S. E., Ngo, H. T., Bai, X., Cheung, W. W. L., Lim, M., Steiner, N., Agard, J., Donatti, C. I., Duarte, C. M., Leemans, R., Managi, S., Pires, A. P. F., Reyes-García, V., Trisos, C., Scholes, R. J., & Pörtner, H.-O. (2022). Governing for Transformative Change across the Biodiversity–Climate–Society Nexus. *BioScience*, 72(7), 684–704. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biac031>
- Patterson, J., Schulz, K., Vervoort, J., Van Der Hel, S., Widerberg, O., Adler, C., Hurlbert, M., Anderton, K., Sethi, M., & Barau, A. (2017). Exploring the governance and politics of transformations towards sustainability. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 24, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2016.09.001>
- Pelling, M., O'Brien, K., & Matyas, D. (2015). Adaptation and transformation. *Climatic Change*, 133(1), 113–127. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-014-1303-0>
- Persson, Å. (2019). Global adaptation governance: An emerging but contested domain. *WIREs Climate Change*, 10(6), e618. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.618>
- Petzold, J., Hawxwell, T., Jantke, K., Gonçalves Gresse, E., Mirbach, C., Ajibade, I., Bhadwal, S., Bowen, K., Fischer, A. P., Joe, E. T., Kirchhoff, C. J., Mach, K. J., Reckien, D., Segnon, A. C., Singh, C., Ulibarri, N., Campbell, D., Cremin, E., Färber, L., ... Garschagen, M. (2023). A global assessment of actors and their roles in climate change adaptation. *Nature Climate Change*, 13(11), 1250–1257. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-023-01824-z>
- Prăvălie, R., Sîrodoev, I., Patriche, C., Roșca, B., Piticar, A., Bandoc, G., Sfică, L., Tișcovschi, A., Dumitrașcu, M., Chifiriuc, C., Mănoiu, V., & Iordache, S. (2020). The impact of climate change on agricultural productivity in Romania. A country-scale assessment based on

- the relationship between climatic water balance and maize yields in recent decades, *Agricultural Systems*, 179, 102767. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2019.102767>
- Okedele, P. O., Aziza, O. R., Oduro, P., & Ishola, A. O. (2024). Integrating indigenous knowledge systems into global climate adaptation policies. *Int J Eng Res Dev*, 20(12), 223-31.
- Quinn, T., Bousquet, F., & Guerbois, C. (2019). Changing places: The role of sense of place in perceptions of social, environmental and overdevelopment risks. *Global Environmental Change*, 57, 101930. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2019.101930>
- Rasmus, S., Turunen, M., Luomaranta, A., Kivinen, S., Jylhä, K., & Rähkä, J. (2020). Climate change and reindeer management in Finland: Co-analysis of practitioner knowledge and meteorological data for better adaptation. *Science of The Total Environment*, 710, 136229. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.136229>
- Rasmus, S., Wallen, H., Turunen, M., Landauer, M., Tahkola, J., Jokinen, M., & Laaksonen, S. (2021). Land-use and climate related drivers of change in the reindeer management system in Finland: Geography of perceptions. *Applied Geography*, 134, 102501. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeog.2021.102501>
- Schakel, A. H. (2020). Multi-level governance in a 'Europe with the regions'. *The British Journal of Politics and International Relations*, 22(4), 767-775.
- Schipper, L. (2006). Conceptual History of Adaptation in the UNFCCC Process. *RECIEL*, 15(1), 82-92.
- Shi, L. (2019). Promise and paradox of metropolitan regional climate adaptation. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 92, 262-274. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2018.11.002>
- Steiger, R., & Trawöger, L. (2011). Klimawandel und Wintertourismus – Ein Vulnerabilitätsprofil für die Region Tirol. *Zeitschrift Für Tourismuswissenschaft*, 3(2), 151-164. <https://doi.org/10.1515/tw-2011-0205>
- Talmaciu, M. (2014). Study on the Relationships between Institutions, Governance and Leadership and Regional Development Policy in Romania. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 15, 1281-1288. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(14\)00589-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(14)00589-9)
- Termeer, C. J. A. M., Dewulf, A., Karlsson-Vinkhuyzen, S. I., Vink, M., & Vliet, M. van. (2016). Coping with the wicked problem of climate adaptation across scales: The Five R Governance Capabilities. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 154, 11-19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2016.01.007>
- Tervo-Kankare, K., Kaján, E., & Saarinen, J. (2018). Costs and benefits of environmental change: Tourism industry's responses in Arctic Finland. *Tourism Geographies*, 20(2), 202-223. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616688.2017.1375973>
- Velea, L., Irimescu, A., Bojariu, R., & Chitu, Z. (2024). Climatic Change and Its Impact on Romanian Rural Tourism – A Review of Actionable Knowledge. *Agriculture*, 14(11), 1917. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture14111917>
- Văidianu, N., Tătui, F., Ristea, M., & Stănică, A. (2020). Managing coastal protection through multi-scale governance structures in Romania. *Marine Policy*, 112, 103567. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2019.103567>
- Van Assche, K., Beunen, R., Verweij, S., Evans, J., & Gruezmacher, M. (2022). Policy Learning and Adaptation in governance; a Co-evolutionary Perspective. *Administration & Society*, 54(7), 1226-1254. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00953997211059165>
- Van Hulst, M., Metz, T., Dewulf, A., De Vries, J., Van Bommel, S., & Van Ostaijen, M. (2024). Discourse, framing and narrative: Three ways of doing critical, interpretive policy analysis. *Critical Policy Studies*, 1-23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19460171.2024.2326936>

- Van Straalen, F. M., Van Den Brink, A., & Van Tatenhove, J. (2016). Integration and decentralization: The evolution of Dutch regional land policy. *International Planning Studies*, 21(2), 148–163. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13563475.2015.1115338>
- Veenman, S., Liefferink, D., & Arts, B. (2009). A short history of Dutch forest policy: The ‘de-institutionalisation’ of a policy arrangement. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 11(3), 202–208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2009.03.001>
- Vij, S., Biesbroek, R., Adler, C., & Muccione, V. (2021). Climate Change Adaptation in European Mountain Systems: A Systematic Mapping of Academic Research. *Mountain Research and Development*, 41(1). <https://doi.org/10.1659/MRD-JOURNAL-D-20-00033.1>
- Visseren-Hamakers, I. J., Razzaque, J., McElwee, P., Turnhout, E., Kelemen, E., Rusch, G. M., Fernández-Llamazares, Á., Chan, I., Lim, M., Islar, M., Gautam, A. P., Williams, M., Mungatana, E., Karim, M. S., Muradian, R., Gerber, L. R., Lui, G., Liu, J., Spangenberg, J. H., & Zaleski, D. (2021). Transformative governance of biodiversity: Insights for sustainable development. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 53, 20–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2021.06.002>
- Vogel, B., Henstra, D., & McBean, G. (2020). Sub-national government efforts to activate and motivate local climate change adaptation: Nova Scotia, Canada. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 22(2), 1633–1653. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-018-0242-8>
- Wiering, M., & Immink, I. (2006). When Water Management Meets Spatial Planning: A Policy-Arrangements Perspective. *Environment and Planning C: Government and Policy*, 24(3), 423–438. <https://doi.org/10.1068/c0417j>
- Wilson, N.J., Lira, M.G. & O’Hanlon, G. (2022). A systematic scoping review of Indigenous governance concepts in the climate governance literature. *Climatic Change* 171, 32. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-022-03354-7>
- Zouwen, M. van der. (2006). *Nature Policy Between Trends and Traditions: Dynamics in Nature Policy Arrangements in the Yorkshire Dales, Doñana, and the Veluwe*. Eburon Uitgeverij B.V.
- Zurba, M., Papadopoulos, A. (2023) Indigenous Participation and the Incorporation of Indigenous Knowledge and Perspectives in Global Environmental Governance Forums: a Systematic Review. *Environmental Management* 72, 84–99. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-021-01566-8>

Annexes

Annex 1. Coding Scheme

Annex 2. Analysed Regional Documents

No.	Title	Year	Scale
Lapland			
LD1	<i>Government Report on Finland's National Climate Change Adaptation Plan until 2030. Wellbeing, Safety and Security in a Changing Climate (NAP2030)</i>	2024	National
LD2	<i>Adaptation to Climate Change in Finland: Current State and Future Prospects</i>	2022	National
Tyrol			
TD1	<i>Leben mit Zukunft. Tiroler Nachhaltigkeits- und Klimastrategie (Tyrolean Sustainability and Climate Strategy)</i>	2021	Regional
TD2	<i>Leben mit Zukunft. Tiroler Nachhaltigkeits- und Klimastrategie. Maßnahmenprogramm 2022-2024 (Tyrolean Sustainability and Climate Strategy. Action Plan 2022-2024)</i>	2022	Regional
TD3	<i>Die Österreichische Strategie zur Anpassung an den Klimawandel (Austrian Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change)</i>	2024	National
Râu Sadului			
RD1	<i>Planul național de acțiune pentru implementarea Strategiei naționale privind adaptarea la schimbările climatice pentru perioada 2023-2030 (National Action Plan for the Implementation of the National Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change for the Period 2023-2030) (PNASC)</i>	n.d.	National
RD2	<i>Strategiei Naționale privind Adaptarea la Schimbările Climatice pentru perioada 2022-2030 cu perspectiva anului 2050 (National Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change for the period 2022-2030 with an outlook to 2050) (SNACS)</i>	n.d.	National
RD3	<i>National Climate Change and Low Carbon Green Growth Strategy 2016-2030</i>	2016	National
RD4	Romania's Sustainable Development Strategy 2030 (SNDDR)	2018	National
RD5	<i>Ghid de bune practici și conștientizare privind atenuarea și adaptarea la schimbările climatice a județul Sibiu (Good Practice and Awareness Raising Guide on Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation in Sibiu County)</i>	2022	Regional
RD6	<i>Strategia și Planul de atenuare și adaptare la schimbările climatice în Municipiul Sibiu (Strategy and Plan for Mitigation and Adaptation to Climate Change in the Municipality of Sibiu) (SPAASC)</i>	2022	Local

Annex 3. Other Documents that were screened

Title	Year	Scale
Lapland		
<i>2022/432 Climate Change Act</i>	2022	National
<i>Carbon Neutral Finland 2035 – National Climate and Energy Strategy</i>	2022	National
<i>Ympäristöhallinnon ilmastonmuutokseen sopeutumisen toimintaohjelma 2022</i> (Climate Change Adaptation Action Plan 2022)	2016	National
<i>Finland's National Climate Change Adaptation Plan 2022</i>	2014	National
<i>Valtioneuvoston selonteko kansallisesta Ilmastonmuutokseen sopeutussuunnitelmasta vuoteen 2030</i> (Government Report on the National Adaptation Plan to Climate Change until 2030)	2022	National
<i>Government Report on the Climate Plan for the Land Use Sector</i>	2023	National
<i>Lapin Green Deal Tiekartta</i> (Lapland Green Deal Roadmap)	2021	National
<i>National Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change</i>	2005	National
<i>Medium-Term Climate Change Policy Plan – Towards a Carbon-Neutral Society in 2035</i>		National
<i>Strategy of the National Commission on Sustainable Development 2022-2030. A Prosperous and Globally Responsible Finland that Protects the Carrying Capacity of Nature</i>	2022	National
<i>Ilmastonmuutokseen liittyvät alueelliset ominaispiirteet ja Haavoittuvuudet Suomessa</i> (Regional Characteristics and Vulnerabilities Related to Climate Change in Finland)	2023	National
<i>Lapin ilmastostrategia 2030</i> (Lapland's Climate Strategy 2030)	2011	Regional
<i>Lapin matkailustrategia 2020-2023</i> (Lapland's Tourism Strategy 2020-2023)	2019	Regional
<i>Lapin matkailustrategia. Päivitys koronatilanteeseen 2021</i> (Lapland's Tourism Strategy 2020-2030. Update on the Corona Situation 2021)	2021	Regional
Tyrol		
<i>Zweiter Fortschrittsbericht zur österreichischen Strategie zur Anpassung an den Klimawandel</i> (Second Progress Report on the Austrian Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change)	2021	National
<i>Fortschrittsbericht 2023 nach §6 Klimaschutzgesetz</i> (Progress Report 2023 in Accordance with §6 of the Climate Protection Act)	2023	National
<i>Plan T – Masterplan für den Tourismus</i> (Plan T- Masterplan for Tourism)	2019	National
<i>Gesamtstaatlicher Hitzeschutzplan</i> (National Heat Protection Plan)	2017	National

<i>Nationaler Klimaresilienz-Check Gesundheit für Gemeinden und Regionen</i> (National Climate Resilience Check on Health for Municipalities and Regions)	2023	National
<i>Klimawandel und Tourismus in Österreich 2030</i> (Climate Change and Tourism in Austria 2030)	2012	National
<i>Tiroler Wirtschafts- und Innovationsstrategie</i> (Tyrolean Economic and Innovation Strategy)	2021	Regional
<i>Der Tiroler Weg – Perspektiven für eine verantwortungsvolle Tourismusentwicklung</i> (The Tyrolean Way – Perspectives for Responsible Tourism Development)	2021	Regional
<i>Strategie für Tirol im Umgang mit gebietsfremden Pflanzenarten (Neophyten)</i> (Strategy for Tyrol for Dealing with Alien Plant Species (Neophytes))	n.d.	Regional
<i>Sachstandbericht Anpassung</i> (Status Report on Adaptation)	2015	Regional
<i>Umsetzung der Tiroler Klimaschutz- und Klimawandelanpassungsstrategie</i> (Implementation of the Tyrolean Climate Protection and Climate Change Adaptation Strategy)	2022	Regional
<i>Klimaszenarien für das Bundesland Tirol bis 2100</i> (Climate Scenarios for the Province of Tyrol until 2100)	2016	Regional
<i>Strategie zur Anpassung an den Klimawandel in Innsbruck</i> (Strategy for Adapting to Climate Change in Innsbruck)	2020	Local
<i>Strategie zur Anpassung an den Klimawandel in Innsbruck. Aktionsplan 2020-2021</i> (Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change in Innsbruck. Action Plan 2020-2021)	2020	Local
Râu Sadului		
Limiting Climate Change and its Impact: An Integrated Approach for Romania	2023	National
Romania's 8th National Communication on Climate Change	2022	National

Annex 4. List of Interviews

No.	Role (pseudonymized)	Date of Interview	Duration of Interview
Lapland			
LI1	Expert in land-use planning at Metsähallitus	March, 23, 2024	47 min
LI2	Expert at Finnish Lapland Tourism Board	March, 20, 2024	41 min
LI3	Expert of Finish Association for Nature Conservation	March, 21, 2024	50 min
LI4	Climate Specialist at ELY	March, 21, 2024	28 min
LI5	Researcher at the University of Lapland	March, 28, 2024	54 min

LI6	Researcher at TYRSKY Consulting	April, 10, 2024	45 min
LI7	Representative of Municipality of Enontekiö	May, 03, 2024	41 min
LI8	Representative of Sámi Reindeer Herders Association	May, 10, 2024	1 hour 07 min
LI9	Sámi Climate Council	May, 23, 2024	Written response
Tyrol			
TI1a, TI1b	Researchers at University of Innsbruck	March, 22, 2024	45min
TI2	Director of a company engaging in winter tourism	March, 27, 2024	52 min
TI3	Researcher at FH Kufstein	April, 09, 2024	45 min
TI4	Regional manager of one of the KLAR! regions	April, 09, 2024	1 hour 04 min
TI5	Representative of a civil society initiative	April, 11, 2024	1 hour 04 min
TI6	Representative of the provincial government	April, 15, 2024	43 min
TI7	Regional manager of one of the KLAR! region	April, 18, 2024	45 min
TI8	Mayor of one Tyrolian municipality	May, 07, 2024	1 hour 10 min
Râu Sadului			
RI1	Scientific Expert at ICDM – Institutul De Cercetare-Dezvoltare PT. Montanologie (Research/Development Institute for Mountainology Christian-Sibiu)	March, 22, 2025	1 hour 34 min
RI2	Scientific Expert at Babeş_– Bolyai University	March, 27, 2024	1 hour 02 min
RI3	Expert at ADRCentru - Agentia pentru Dezvoltare Regionala Centru (Regional Development Agency Centru)	April, 10, 2024	51 min
RI4	Expert at Sibiu County Council	April, 23, 2024	47 min
RI5	Expert at FUNDATIA ADEPT	May, 10, 2024	40 min

Annex 5. Interview Guideline

(depending on the background of the interviewee, not all of the following questions were asked)

1. What are distinctive features of the region?
 - a) What are the region's strengths and weaknesses?
 - b) What are key challenges that need to be tackled?
 - c) How should the region continue to develop?

2. From your own observation and experience, are there specific strategies or laws that influence CCA activities in the region?
 - a) Would you say that there are concrete strategies and regulations missing? Which ones, in what area or regarding which issues?
3. What are the most pressing challenges of CCA in the region?
4. How long has your region been engaged with CCA? Is it a rather new topic or been on the agenda for quite some time?
 - a) What triggered its agenda-setting?
 - b) What would you consider key milestones in tackling climate change adaptation? (e.g. regulation/law coming into place, implementation of a key project, engagement of central actor etc.)
5. Who is pushing climate change adaptation forward in the region?
 - a) Which administrative level is mainly engaging with climate change adaptation? (international/EU/national/regional/local)
 - b) Who would you consider key stakeholders/institutions (e.g. businesses, NGOs,...)?
 - c) What role does civil society play in climate change adaptation?
6. What would be the best-case scenario for CCA in the region?
 - a) How could you get there? Who would need to be involved? (actors, instruments (e.g. governmental, economical/financial, informational), technologies etc.)
 - b) What are major challenges that (could) hinder successful CCA? (behaviours/values, practices, etc.)

Annex 6. Validation Workshops (VDWS)

The workshops were conducted in an online format. The online tool Miro was used to facilitate visualization of discussion points.

Abbreviation	Region	Date and Duration	Participants
LVDWS	Lapland	June 17, 2024, from 14:00 to 16:00 (EEST)	21
TVDWS	Tyrol	June 20, 2024, from 08:30 to 10:30 (EEST)	16
RVDWS	Râu Sadului	June 25, 2024, from 09:00 to 11:00 (EEST)	16